

1 **PRDM14 is active in human pluripotent stem cells and silenced during TE commitment.**

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7 We measured total transcription in the inner cell mass (ICM) and the trophectoderm (TE) of the human
8 embryo to understand the mechanisms underlying TE commitment. We describe here discovery of
9 Prdm14 as a lineage commitment factor or lineage commitment cooperating factor in embryonic stem cells
10 of the human embryo. PRDM1 was also active during this developmental transition in the human embryo.

11 Citations

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